

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

This is the supplementary material (<https://doi.org/10.61733/jconch/4549s>) to the article:

SALVADOR RB, FERREIRA-SANTOS L, CAVALLARI DC, BICHUETTE ME. 2025. First report of Eucalodiidae in Brazil (Stylommatophora: Urocoptoidea), with description of a new genus and species. *Journal of Conchology* **45** (3): 580–588. doi: <https://doi.org/10.61733/jconch/4549>

Below are presented additional CT scan images of *Caerbannogia calida* gen et. sp. nov. (holotype LES 6873) and *Brasilennea arethusae* Maury, 1935 (specimens MZSP 86322 and 86324A).

Caerbannogia calida gen et. sp. nov., holotype LES 6873.

Brasilennea arethusae Maury, 1935, specimen MZSP, 86322.

Brasilennea arethusae Maury, 1935, specimen MZSP, 86324A.